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Singing vocal source separation on Jingju Music

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Abstract

This thesis addresses the challenge of vocal source separation in Jingju (Peking Opera) music through three key objectives. First, it introduces a multi-track dataset (JMTRC) specifically designed for Jingju, featuring isolated vocal and instrumental tracks meticulously recorded and annotated for training and evaluating source separation models. Second, it examines the applicability of existing source separation models, originally trained on popular music, to Jingju music, revealing their limitations due to the unique acoustic properties and complex interactions characteristic of Jingju. Third, the study explores the enhancement of these models through fine-tuning with the Jingju dataset, demonstrating substantial improvements in separation quality as evidenced by increased Scale-Invariant Signal-to-Distortion Ratio (Si-SDR) and perceptual quality metrics. Overall, this research contributes to computational ethnomusicology by providing a specialized dataset and methodologies for Jingju vocal separation, with implications for the preservation and promotion of this traditional music through advanced digital techniques.

Keywords: Jingju Music; Vocal Source Separation; Computational Ethnomusicology; Dataset Construction; Fine-tune Model

Chapter 1

Introduction

1.1 Motivation and Goals

Jingju is renowned for its special vocal forms and interleaving instrumental accompaniments, posing unique challenges for traditional music source separation techniques. Existing methods often perform poorly when dealing with Jingju music, a particularly prominent issue. Jingju, a unique form of stage art, makes acquiring unaccompanied pure Jingju vocal recordings both difficult and costly. However, such pure Jingju vocal recordings are crucial for academic research (such as computational ethnomusicology analysis and digital archiving) and practical applications (e.g., improving recording quality and developing remixing materials).

This study aims to explore and improve music source separation methods by investigating the musicological factors contributing to the poor performance of existing approaches when applied to Jingju. The main motivation of this research is to develop effective techniques for separating vocal tracks in Jingju music. Consequently, the primary objective of this thesis is to create and empirically validate a source separation model specifically tailored for extracting vocals from Jingju music. This objective is pursued through several key initiatives:

- **Construction of a New Specialized Dataset:** Develop a multi-track dataset of Jingju music incorporating isolated vocal and instrumental tracks. This dataset will

serve as a foundational resource for the training and evaluation of source separation models, ensuring that the models are tested under conditions that reflect the unique complexities of Jingju performances.

- **Adaptation of Existing Technologies:** Improve and refine advanced source separation model to align with the distinct acoustic properties of Jingju music. This adaptation aims to enhance the performance and reliability of these technologies when applied to Jingju, addressing discrepancies in pitch range overlap and timbral characteristics inherent in traditional Chinese opera.
- **Contribution to Computational Ethnomusicology:** Investigate and document the specific challenges Jingju music poses to conventional source separation models. This research will contribute insights into the limitations of current models when applied to non-Western musical forms, supporting broader efforts in digital preservation and detailed musical analysis. The findings are expected to provide both theoretical and practical contributions to the field of computational ethnomusicology, particularly in understanding the musical structures that hinder effective source separation.

Through these initiatives, this thesis has developed a source separation tool specifically designed for Jingju music. This tool enhances our ability to analyze and preserve the intricate details of traditional Chinese opera in a culturally sensitive and technically sophisticated manner. The goal is to advance music analysis tools that are both culturally sensitive and technically sophisticated, facilitating a deeper understanding and preservation of traditional Chinese opera.

1.2 Music Source Separation

Blind Source Separation (BSS) is a technique designed to separate source signals from a set of mixed signals with minimal understanding of these sources or their mixing processes. BSS primarily addresses how to reconstruct original signals from mixed signals. In practical applications, there are generally three types of mixing systems: *multi-channel source separation*, *single-channel source separation*, and *deconvolution-based separation* [1]. Here, these three methods will be briefly explored:

Figure 1: Cocktail party problem scenario. Adapted from [1].

In *multi-channel separation*, the classical cocktail party problem, introduced by Cherry in 1953 [2], involves multiple simultaneous conversations within a single acoustic environment. A listener's goal is to isolate and focus on the speech of a particular individual. Figure 1 illustrates a typical scenario of this problem, serving as an example of how such situations can be represented. This problem can be represented by a 3×3 linear mixing system: $\mathbf{x}_t = \mathbf{A}\mathbf{s}_t$, where \mathbf{x}_t is the mixed signal, \mathbf{s}_t is the source signal, and \mathbf{A} is the mixing matrix. If \mathbf{A} is invertible, we can recover the original source signals \mathbf{s}_t using the demixing matrix $\mathbf{W} = \mathbf{A}^{-1}$.

When the number of channels equals the number of source signals, the system is **determined** and has a unique solution. This means the number of microphones is equal to the number of source signals, and this problem can be resolved by Independent Component Analysis (ICA). When the number of channels exceeds the number of source signals, the system is **overdetermined**, often leading to inconsistencies in the equations. In this case, complex-valued ICA methods can be used to separate the frequency band mixtures. When the number of channels is less than the number of source signals, the system is **underdetermined**, making it difficult to find reliable solutions. Time-frequency masking schemes can be used, estimating the separate signals for each source using the Short-Time Fourier Transform (STFT) and clustering.

The *single-channel source separation* typically involves a single recording channel mixed

Figure 2: Monaural source separation using three sources. Adapted from [1].

or convoluted with various sources or interference, as shown in Figure 2. This example depicts a scenario of mono source separation using a single microphone with three sources, but it is important to note that the number of sources can vary. Source separation aims to suppress surrounding noise, such as birds and planes, and to isolate human voices for listening or understanding purposes. Thus, single-channel source separation is often employed as a method for voice enhancement or noise reduction, focusing on purifying the speech signal amidst ambient noise. This technique is applicable not only to speech but also to **music source separation**, aiming to isolate and enhance specific audio elements from a complex acoustic mix.

The *deconvolution-based separation* focuses on indoor reverberant environments, where sound waves emitted by loudspeakers or other sound sources propagate within a room and reflect multiple times off surfaces such as walls. These reflections alter the acoustic properties of the sound waves and cause the audio signals to undergo complex convolution mixing. Reverberant environments significantly affect the clarity of speech and increase the difficulty of audio signal processing and separation. The goal of dereverberation source separation is to recover the original clear speech signals from environments filled with reflections, thereby enhancing speech intelligibility and communication efficiency.

In practical applications, source separation is mainly used in the following scenarios: Speech Separation, Music Separation, Audio Source Separation, Biomedical Source Separation, Image Separation, Text Mining, etc. This thesis focuses more on music source separation.

Music Information Retrieval (MIR) is a dynamic and expanding field of research. A

Figure 3: Diagram of music source separation.

critical challenge within MIR is dealing with music signals that are often a complex amalgamation of various instruments, singing voices, and sound effects. Such complexity can significantly degrade the performance of MIR systems.

To solve these issues, music separation is employed, aiming to decompose a music piece into distinct tracks per instrument or sound source. As shown in Figure 3.

This separation is pivotal as it significantly enhances the accuracy and efficiency of the retrieval processes in MIR applications. Two of the most critical tasks in this area are instrumental music separation and singing voice separation.

The **instrumental music separation** focuses on isolating individual instruments within a mixed signal—such as piano, flute, drum, and violin—by identifying and leveraging their unique acoustic characteristics. Understanding these characteristics allows MIR systems to differentiate and isolate the sounds of various instruments more effectively.

In contrast, **singing voice separation** deals with extracting the vocal component from a music track. The vocal track is rich with information about the song's emotional content and the singer's identity, which is valuable for a variety of music-related applications. These include *singer identification*, where the unique timbre and style of a vocalist are analyzed; *singing quality evaluation*, which assesses performance for training or competitive purposes; and more complex tasks like *music emotion recognition*, *melody extraction*, *lyric recognition*, and synchronization of lyrics with music. Typically, the singing voice is embedded within a dense mix of background accompaniments, making its isolation challenging yet critical for enhancing the utility of MIR.

This section introduces the fundamental concepts and principles of source separation,

and explains how these technologies can be integrated with Music Information Retrieval (MIR). From these principles, it is evident that music source separation technologies are well-suited for tasks involving the extraction of vocals in Jingju because this task can be considered a task of separating vocals from various instrumental sources.

1.3 Jingju (Peking Opera) Music

Jingju (京剧), also known as Peking Opera, originated in the late 18th century and became highly popular in Beijing during the Qing Dynasty, hence its name. Jingju is a fusion of several older forms of Chinese opera, particularly Huiju (徽剧) from Anhui and Hanju (汉剧) from Hubei, which were brought to Beijing and gradually merged to create this distinctive form of performance.

One of the most remarkable features of Jingju is its combination of singing, dialogue, acting, and acrobatics. The vocal performance in Jingju is characterized by its specific tonal patterns and rhythmic qualities, often delivered in a high-pitched, melodic style. The spoken dialogue is performed in a stylized manner to enhance the dramatic effect.

Acting in Jingju involves precise, exaggerated movements, including hand gestures, body postures, and facial expressions that convey the emotions and actions of the characters. The acrobatic aspect, especially in martial scenes, showcases the physical prowess and agility of the performers, with complex flips, spins, and combat sequences.

Another hallmark of Jingju is its use of elaborate costumes and makeup. Each role type has specific costumes and facial makeup designs that indicate their personality, social status, and role within the story. The vibrant colors and intricate patterns of the costumes, along with the symbolic facial makeup, create a visually striking performance.

Overall, Jingju is a rich and complex art form that embodies the essence of traditional Chinese culture through its unique blend of music, drama, and acrobatics. Given the specialized terminology and instruments in Jingju, understanding these elements is crucial. The following sections provide an introduction to key terms and instruments, primarily based on the *Encyclopedia of Beijing Opera* [3]. This work is the most extensive and authoritative literature on Jingju, compiled by leading scholars in the field. Consequently, most of the following explanations of Jingju terms are derived from this comprehensive

source.

1.3.1 Introduction to Most Relevant Jingju Terms

The first term to introduce is the “Jingju repertoire” (剧目), which refers to a collection of works that a troupe or actor can perform, similar to the term of repertoire in Western opera. A single work within Jingju is known as a “Jingju play” (戏). The current Jingju repertoire comprises approximately 1,400 plays. Each play features unique storylines, characters, and themes, often drawing from Chinese historical tales, folk legends, classical literature, or significant historical events.

Another term in Jingju is the “Jingju excerpt” (唱段), which refers to selected segments from a larger play. These segments are chosen for their significance, showcasing particular highlights of the performance, such as key arias or dramatic moments. This is similar to the term “excerpt” in Western contexts, which denotes a short extract from a longer piece of music, literature, or performance. Additionally, because this thesis aims to study Jingju vocal source separation, only the musical parts of Jingju were recorded. Therefore, referring to these segments as “arias” is more accurate in this thesis.

Furthermore, a key term in Jingju performance is the “*hangdang*” (行当, role type), which categorizes the various roles in Jingju. On the Jingju stage, roles are classified based on factors such as gender, personality, age, occupation, and social status. These roles are artistically exaggerated through makeup, costume, and performance. The role types are broadly divided into four main categories:

- *sheng* (生): This role type includes male roles other than *jing* and *chou*. The type of *sheng* appearing in this thesis is the *laosheng* (老生), depicting middle-aged or older men. Performers in the *laosheng* role use their full voice, with *shengqiang* primarily consisting of *xipi* and *erhuang*, featuring a rich variety of *banshi*. The singing style is stable, expansive, vigorous, and smooth.
- *dan* (旦): This role type includes female roles. The three main types of *dan* in this thesis are *huadan* (花旦), *qingyi* (青衣), and *laodan* (老旦). In Jingju, *huadan*, *qingyi*, and *laodan* are principally distinguished by the character’s age. The *huadan* depicts vibrant, often coquettish young women, performed with a falsetto that is fluid and vivacious, utilizing vocal techniques such as vibrato,

tremolo, glissando, portamento, staccato, and breathy tones. The *qingyi* represents middle-aged women and is a critical category, also using falsetto, with styles varying by school. The *laodan* represents elderly women, singing in their full voice, embodying a robust yet graceful style with rich tones and intricate melodies.

- *jing* (净): This role type usually features colorful face paint. The *jing* roles depict male characters who are either heroic and bold or rugged and reckless. Their voice is loud and broad, characterized by a rough and unrestrained quality.
- *chou* (丑): This role type often plays comical, humorous, and witty roles. The *chou* actors use their full voice when singing, but these roles have fewer singing parts and lack distinctive vocal characteristics.

Finally, the concept of “*changqiang*” (唱腔; translated as “singing style”) refers to the vocal performance in Jingju music. The *changqiang* includes two important elements: *shengqiang* (声腔), which describes the melody, and *banshi* (板式), which defines the rhythm.

The main *shengqiang* are *xipi* (西皮) and *erhuang* (二黄). The *jinghu* tuning for *xipi* is “6 ~ 3”. The melody is lively, high-pitched, and powerful, with bright colors and variable rhythm, often expressing joyful and cheerful emotions. The *jinghu* tuning for *erhuang* is “5 ~ 2”, with starting and ending notes on the beat. The melody has gentle fluctuations and a steady rhythm, suitable for expressing reserved and calm emotions. The timbre is warm and layered, often depicting calm and solemn states, conveying deep emotions.

There are 14 common *banshi*, which are interrelated. For example, the *yuanban* (原板) is usually the default mode for a medium tempo, while other *banshi* such as the *manban* (慢板) and *kuaiban* (快板) are variants of it, realized by slowing down and speeding up the tempo of the *yuanban*, respectively.

1.3.2 Introduction to Most Relevant Jingju Instruments

To understand the common instruments used in Jingju, it is essential to first grasp the concept of “*changmian*” (场面; translated as “orchestral ensemble”), which is specific to Jingju performances.

This ensemble varies depending on the scene type: “*wenchang*” (文场; translated as “melodic ensemble”), typically used in civil scenes, and “*wuchang*” (武场; translated as “percussion ensemble”), typically used in martial scenes. The melodic ensemble employs orchestral instruments to accompany narrative sections, with foundational instruments such as the *jinghu*, *yueqin*, and *sanxian* playing central roles. Additional instruments in the melodic ensemble may include the *jingerhu*, *daruan*, and *zhongruan*. Conversely, the percussion ensemble emphasizes percussion instruments, which are crucial for enhancing dramatic martial arts scenes. Key instruments include the *bangu*, large-gong, small-gong, and cymbals.

Subsequently, the instruments included in this thesis will be introduced, focusing on their unique sound characteristics and roles in accompaniment:

- *jinghu* (京胡): The *jinghu* is a Chinese bowed string instrument used in Jingju and belongs to the *huqin* family. Officially named *jinghu* in the 1950s, it is the smallest and highest-pitched instrument in the *huqin* family. The sound of the *jinghu* is similar to that of the violin but sharper. Its image is shown in Figure 4a. The accompaniment style of the *jinghu* is closely related to the styles of different Jingju schools. However, regardless of the school, the essence of the *jinghu* accompaniment style is based on the performance characteristics of the instrument, aiming to support and imitate the style features of the singer. This results in a sound quite similar to the human voice in Jingju, in terms of pitch range, timbre, and cadential structure. This has been widely mentioned in the literature related to Jingju (e.g., [4, 5]).
- *yueqin* (月琴): The *yueqin*, also called a moon lute or moon guitar, is a traditional Chinese string instrument. It is a lute with a round, hollow soundboard, a short fretted neck, and usually four strings. It is an important instrument in the Jingju orchestra, often taking the role of the main melodic instrument, replacing the bowed string section. Its sound is soft and clear, complementing vocal performances with its bright, resonant tones. Its image is shown in Figure 4b. Similar to the *jinghu*, the *yueqin*'s playing techniques vary among different schools and play a key role in expressing emotions. However, unlike the *jinghu*, the primary playing techniques of the *yueqin* include staccato, plucking, and continuous rolls. These methods contribute to the *yueqin*'s unique sound, characterized by a grainy

texture [6, 7].

- *sanxian* (三弦): The *sanxian* is a traditional Chinese lute with three strings. It features a long, fretless fingerboard, and its body is traditionally made from snake skin stretched over a rounded rectangular resonator. The *sanxian* is available in several sizes for different purposes. It produces a dry, somewhat percussive tone and has a loud volume, similar to that of a *banjo*. The larger sizes of the *sanxian* have a range of three octaves. Its image is shown in Figure 4c. Due to its distinct dry and resonant tone, coupled with its considerable volume, the *sanxian* is utilized in Jingju music primarily to accompany roles such as *laosheng*, *laodan*, and *jing*. These role types are characterized by robust vocal delivery, which the *sanxian* complements effectively due to its strong and penetrating sound [8].
- Other Melodic Instruments: In addition to the main three instruments, the melodic ensemble in Jingju may also include the *jingerhu* (京二胡) and the *ruan* (阮). The *jingerhu*, developed from the *jinghu*, provides a thicker middle range to support *dan* roles. The *ruan*, a traditional Chinese plucked string instrument, is available in various sizes such as the *zhongruan* (中阮) and *daruan* (大阮), covering different pitch ranges. These instruments fill out the middle and lower registers of Jingju music, complementing the primary instruments. Their images are shown in Figure 5.
- Percussion Instruments: The primary percussion instruments used are the *bangu* (板鼓), large-gong (大锣), cymbals (铙钹), and small-gong (小锣). The *bangu* setup includes a single-headed drum and a wooden clapper; the drum is utilized for the offbeat and weaker beats and varies rhythmically, whereas the clapper marks the strong beats, collectively supporting the melodic lines and staged movements. The large-gong, a circular brass instrument, varies in pitch and is typically used to emphasize the entrance and exit of generals and to synchronize with combat scenes. Cymbals, made of two clashed brass discs, serve versatile roles in bridging rhythms and intensifying the auditory impact of the percussion section. The small-gong, similar in material but smaller in size, produces a distinct, clear tone available in high, medium, and low pitches, and is often employed to accompany various characters and narrative progressions. These percussion instruments are shown in Figure 6.

Figure 4: The main instruments of melodic ensemble in Jingju.

Figure 5: The other instruments of melodic ensemble in Jingju.

(a) The *bangu*.

(b) The large-gong.

(c) The cymbals.

(d) The small-gongs.

Figure 6: The instruments of percussion ensemble in Jingju.

Chapter 2

State of the Art

This chapter reviews the latest advancements in the literature related to the topic of this work. It specifically focuses on the methodologies of music source separation and the existing datasets available for training. A particular emphasis is placed on the studies concerning source separation isolation in Jingju music. Through this summary, the chapter aims to provide critical insights and valuable information that will be instrumental in addressing the challenges posed by our research tasks.

2.1 Music Source Separation Model

2.1.1 Source Separation Modeling for General Music

The problem of music source separation has been extensively researched over the past two decades, leading to the development of various methods. These can be broadly categorized into traditional and deep learning-based approaches.

Initially, music source separation relied on traditional signal processing methods like principal component analysis (PCA) [9], non-negative matrix factorization (NMF) [10], and multichannel non-negative matrix factorization [11]. These methods were effective to a degree and valued for their interpretability. However, their performance depended heavily on the specific characteristics of the music data, limiting their use in complex musical scenarios. This limitation prompted the shift towards deep learning-based approaches, especially over the last decade. With improvements in computational power and the

adaptability of neural networks for GPU-based training, deep learning has become a dominant approach in music source separation, moving the field from knowledge-based to data-driven methods.

Deep learning models in music source separation are typically categorized based on the data they process: frequency-domain models, which excel with spectral features, and time-domain models, which handle raw audio waveforms directly. Time-domain models, like the Wave-U-Net [12], capture phase information by working directly in the waveform domain, avoiding the loss of phase details and enabling low-latency computations. These models generally use 1-D convolutional layers and encoder-decoder structures with skip connections as shown in figure 7, which help retain the original audio's magnitude and phase information. Notable models include the Demucs [13], Wavenet [14], and Spleeter [15]. Spleeter, particularly, stands out for its ease of use, performance, and speed, being highly effective in 4-stem separation tasks. Sivasankar, A. 's thesis [16] explored the fine-tuning of the pre-trained Spleeter model with a new dataset of isolated Carnatic music stems, improving its ability to separate vocals from complex instrumental backgrounds in Carnatic music. The retrained Spleeter model showed a 1.1 dB increase in the Source-to-Distortion ratio (SDR) compared to the baseline model. Additionally, there are time-domain models without the U-Net structure [17, 18, 19], like those proposed by Yi Luo, based on the encoder-decoder linear structure proposed in [17], with gradual improvements.

Frequency-domain models, being similar to traditional methods, have a deeper research base. The CWSPResUNet [20] is one such model, which is an extension of the phase-aware ResUNet [21] and uses the channel-wise subband feature [22]. This model, unlike older systems, estimates the phase of separated sources, resulting in improved music source separation performance. When tested, CWSP-ResUNet achieved notable results in vocal separation SDR. After combining these two methods, CWS-PResUNet [20] reached a vocal separation SDR of 8.92dB and an average separation SDR of 6.77 dB when tested on the MUSDB18HQ dataset after training with the MUSDB18HQ dataset. Another promising model is the Attentive-MultiResUNet [23], which introduces an attention mechanism and uses Short-time Discrete Cosine Transform (STDCT) instead of traditional Short-Time Fourier Transform (STFT) time-frequency representation input. This

Figure 7: Structure of Wave-U-Net. Figure from [12]

makes the model less complex and computationally intensive, while still delivering comparable performance.

The Hybrid Transformer Demucs (HT Demucs) model [24] currently leads in popular music source separation. This architecture is a hybrid temporal/spectral bi-UNet, incorporating a cross-domain Transformer Encoder that utilizes self-attention within one domain and cross-attention across domains. The study demonstrates that HT-Demucs, when trained with an extra 800 songs, surpasses the performance of the Hybrid Demucs model [25] by 0.45 dB of SDR. By employing sparse attention kernels and per source fine-tuning, the model achieves state-of-the-art results on the MUSDB dataset with a remarkable 9.20 dB of average SDR. This research highlights the effectiveness of transformers in handling long-range contextual information in music source separation.

The best performing method in the separation of vocal parts from popular music sources is the Band-split RNN (BSRNN) model [26] proposed by Luo et al. in 2022. This frequency-domain model consists of three modules, a band split module, a sequence and band modeling module, and a mask estimation module. It enhances performance

of MSS by splitting a spectrogram into subbands, which allows for detailed band-level and sequence-level modeling, particularly effective for high sample rate signals and targeting specific musical instruments. The paper also presents a unique semi-supervised fine-tuning pipeline utilizing unlabeled data and a self-boosting scheme, significantly improving performance over existing models. After training with MUSDB18 and fine-tuning over 1.7 K extra music tracks, its average SDR in tests on the MUSDB18 dataset was 8.97 dB, while the vocal SDR was 10.47 dB. This advancement demonstrates BSRNN's potential for broader applications in various musical genres and audio extraction tasks, highlighting its robustness and adaptability.

The most recent works on music source separation are [27, 28]. They are focus more on how to improve the robustness of music source separation than other previous works to improve the separation performance of music source separation. This is because in most cases, the data used to train the model is not ideal, e.g., the training data is mislabelled (label-noise), the training data is bleeding, etc. Especially, in [28], Plaja-Roglans et al. achieved good results using a cold diffusion model trained by bleeding data for source separation on Indian Carnatic music.

2.1.2 Source Separation Modeling for Jingju Music

While the field of music source separation has advanced considerably over the years, its application in Jingju music remains relatively unexplored and incidental. This section talks about the limited yet notable attempts made in source separation specifically for Jingju music although these endeavors are often secondary to other primary research objectives.

The earliest current work to make an attempt related to source separation in Jingju music was presented by Tian et al. in 2014 in their paper [29]. In this article, they introduced a method for detecting the onsets of Jingju percussion instruments using a non-negative matrix factorisation (NMF) based algorithm. This approach significantly improves the accuracy of onset detection by separating ensemble recordings into distinct sound sources using NMF, a technique widely applied in audio and music analysis for extracting structured components from complex audio signals. Subsequently, in 2016, Tian et al. [30] employed the Harmonic-Percussion Sound Source Separation (HPSS) technique primar-

ily for the musical structure segmentation of Jingju. HPSS is an approximation to the concept of sound source separation, which separates the input complex spectrogram into harmonic and percussive components and in this way, extracts the features required for the analysis.

Finally, the latest to apply source separation techniques to Jingju music are Gong et al., as documented in [31]. They adapted the low-latency monaural source separation CNN framework, proposed by Pritish Chandna et al. in [32], for Jingju music source separation. This framework, a state-of-the-art approach at the time, was employed in constructing the Cappella Singing Audio Dataset for Automatic Jingju Singing Evaluation Research. However, this algorithm struggled to produce a clean singing voice while maintaining its inherent characteristics, as noted in [31].

2.2 Dataset used for Source Separation

2.2.1 General Music Source Separation Dataset

This section reviews the datasets commonly utilized in training music source separation models, with detailed descriptions based on their release dates presented in the following subsections.

In 2014, Bittner, R., et al. introduced MelodyDB [33], a royalty-free, annotated multi-track recording dataset containing 122 multitracks with melodic annotations. This diverse collection includes 30 songs from independent artists, 32 from NYU's Dolan Recording Studio, 25 from Weathervane Music, and 35 from Music Delta. Predominantly recorded in professional studios and mixed by experienced engineers, these tracks cover a range of nine musical genres, including rock and classical. MelodyDB offers three types of audio content for each song: remixes, stems, and raw audio. All audio files are in .wav format, featuring a sample rate of 44.1 kHz and a 16-bit depth. While the mixes and stems are stereo, the raw audio files are mono. Each track is complemented by metadata in a YAML file, detailing information such as the artist, composer, and instrumentation. Primarily designed to support melody extraction research, MelodyDB also proves invaluable for tasks like source separation and automated mixing. A subsequent enhancement, MelodyDB 2.0 [34], was released in 2016, adding 74 multitracks to the original dataset.

Figure 8: Components of the MUSDB18. Figure from <https://sigsep.github.io/datasets/musdb.html>

In 2017, the MUSDB18 dataset [35] was launched, rapidly becoming essential in music source separation research. As of today, MUSDB18 serves as the primary baseline dataset for training and evaluating audio source separation models. This dataset comprises 150 full-length music tracks, totaling approximately 10 hours and encompassing a variety of genres. It includes isolated stems for drums, bass, vocals, and others, as depicted in figure 8. MUSDB18 is organized into two sections: a "train" folder with 100 songs and a "test" folder containing 50 songs. Supervised models are generally trained on the "train" set and evaluated on both. All tracks are stereophonic, encoded at a 44.1kHz sample rate. The dataset sources its tracks from multiple origins: 100 from the DSD100 [36], 46 from MedleyDB [34], two provided by Native Instruments, and two from the Canadian rock band The Easton Ellises. Additionally, an uncompressed variant, MUSDB18-HQ [37], offers WAV files suitable for high-bandwidth predictions of up to 22 kHz, while maintaining the same structure as MUSDB18.

Finally, released in 2019, the Slakh2100 [38] dataset is the latest advancement for music source separation and multi-instrument automated transcription. As the largest open dataset available, Slakh2100 comprises 2100 automatically mixed tracks along with corresponding MIDI files, resulting in 145 hours of mixtures. These are divided into training (1500 tracks), validation (375 tracks), and test (225 tracks) subsets. Slakh2100 is derived from the Lakh MIDI dataset (LMD) and features high-quality renderings of instrumental mixtures and corresponding stems created using professional-grade sample-based virtual instruments. Although it serves as a potent tool for music source separation and complements other datasets like MUSDB18, Slakh2100's notable difference is its exclusion

of isolated vocal sources, attributable to the MIDI standard's limitation in supporting vocals. Consequently, this dataset may not be as effective for tasks involving vocal-accompaniment separation.

2.2.2 Previous Jingju Music Dataset

Right now, there aren't any datasets made just for separating music sources in jingju. But, there's a dataset from the CompMusic ¹ project by the UPF Music Technology Group that might be helpful. This dataset is called the Jingju a Cappella Recordings Collection (JaCRC)[39]. Gong et al. introduced its final version in 2022. It's mainly for studying the melodies of jingju arias and the way words are pronounced in jingju.

What makes JaCRC useful for separating sources in jingju music is that it has 314 recordings of jingju a cappella singing and 76 recordings of Jinghu, which is the accompanying music. The main body of the JaCRC are 239 a cappella recordings of jingju arias. Out of these, 186 are new recordings by professional or semi-professional singers. Also, they added 53 a cappella jingju recordings from the Singing Voice Audio Dataset² with permission of their authors.

¹<https://compmusic.upf.edu/>

²<http://isophonics.net/SingingVoiceDataset>

Chapter 3

A Multi-Track Dataset for Jingju Vocal Source Separation

To accomplish the task of vocal source separation for Jingju, it is necessary to construct a dataset specifically for this purpose. This dataset should contain the ground truth input data, including Jingju’ s complete mixed audio frequency, as well as the ground truth output data of separated vocal and accompaniment audio. This chapter introduces the first significant contribution of this thesis: the construction of the Jingju Multi-Track Recordings Collection (JMTRC). The JMTRC serves as a valuable tool for researchers and practitioners in the field of Jingju.

The JMTRC is crucial for both research and practical applications, particularly in Jingju vocal separation. Additionally, the JMTRC is well-organized and rich in content, offering great potential for other computational ethnomusicological studies based on Jingju.

3.1 Recording the Dataset

3.1.1 Artists

During the recording process of the JMTRC, we invited professional actors and musicians from the Linyi City Cultural Hall and the Shandong Province Jingju Theatre. A total of 20 singers and 10 musicians participated (some of whom also participated in the singing). All participants are experts in the Jingju field, including several State First-Class Artists,

with extensive stage performance and music-playing experience. These artists performed a series of selected classic arias. The specific list of singers and musicians can be found in Table 1.

Table 1: Detailed information of the recording artists, including role name, role type, and affiliation. LWCC: Linyi Workers’ Culture Center, SPJT: Shandong Province Jingju Theater

Role	Name	Role-type	Affiliation	Note
Singer	曹现桂	<i>qingyi</i>	LWCC	
	韩丽成	<i>hualian</i>	LWCC	
	康金云	<i>huadan</i>	LWCC	
	李新清	<i>laosheng</i>	SPJT	
	李红霞	<i>qingyi</i>	SPJT	first-class artist
	路占华	<i>laosheng</i>	SPJT	
	马济生	<i>hualian</i>	SPJT	first-class artist
	孟庆虎	<i>laosheng</i>	SPJT	
	孙萍	<i>qingyi</i>	LWCC	
	王瑞竹	<i>qingyi</i>	LWCC	
	王玉梅	<i>laodan</i>	SPJT	
	徐芳	<i>qingyi</i>	LWCC	
	徐莉	<i>qingyi</i>	LWCC	
	徐小雅	<i>qingyi</i>	LWCC	
	薛莉民	<i>qingyi</i>	LWCC	
	谢涛	<i>laosheng</i>	SPJT	
	杨云娥	<i>qingyi</i>	LWCC	
	赵青	<i>laodan</i>	LWCC	
	赵晖	<i>laosheng</i>	SPJT	
	钟建萍	<i>qingyi</i>	SPJT	
Player	管运浓	<i>jinghu</i>	LWCC	
	何振清	<i>jinghu</i>	SPJT	first-class artist
	胡卫萍	<i>jingerhu</i>	SPJT	

Continued on next page

Role	Name	Role-type	Affiliation	Note
	李海涛	<i>yueqin</i>	SPJT	
	刘景玲	<i>daruan</i>	LWCC	
	刘树枫	<i>yueqin</i>	LWCC	
	刘永健	<i>zhongruan</i>	LWCC	
	石世平	<i>jinghu</i>	LWCC	
		<i>jing'erhu</i>		
	孙家生	<i>sanxian</i>	LWCC	
	孙萍	<i>yueqin</i>	LWCC	
		<i>zhongruan</i>		
	谢涛	<i>jinghu</i>	LWCC	
	吴维同	<i>jing'erhu</i>	LWCC	
	王佃标	percussion	LWCC	
	杨清华	percussion	LWCC	
	于言武	<i>zhongruan</i>	SPJT	
	李志	percussion	SPJT	

3.1.2 Recording Setup

During the recording session for the JMTRC, the *jinghu* was initially recorded in isolation. The *jinghu* player controlled the emotional intensity and timing of the piece. Subsequently, the recordings of the *jingerhu*, *yueqin*, *zhongruan*, percussion, and vocal parts were conducted. These sessions were guided by the playback of the *jinghu*'s recording through headphones, allowing each musician to play or sing independently. Every instrument and vocal was recorded on separate tracks, using a two-channel setup to achieve a stereo effect.

- **Set 1:** Two Audio-Technica AT4050 condenser microphones + M-Audio Octane 8-channel preamplifier + RME HDSPE Alo Pro PCI-E sound card + Samplitude X5 DAW.
- **Set 2:** LEWITT 840 tube condenser microphone + Waves DigiGrid preamplifier/sound card + Pro Tools 2023 DAW.

- **Room 1:** Located at the Linyi Workers’ Cultural Center, this standard recording studio is outfitted with walls lined with soundproof panels and multiple layers of sound-absorbing panels. It also features carpeted flooring and maintains a noise-free environment.
- **Room 2:** Located at Shandong Radio and Television, this small recording studio adheres to acoustical standards and is fitted with sound-absorbing panels, reflective panels, and diffusers.

Finally, two professional audio engineers¹ mixed all the separate tracks into two versions: a complete Jingju mixture with both vocals and accompaniment, and an accompaniment-only version mixed from the individual instrument tracks.

3.2 Description of the Jingju Music dataset

During the recording process, we conducted five sessions, ultimately obtaining a ground truth dataset JMTRC, containing 45 Jingju arias, totaling 4 hours and 5 minutes. As the JMTRC is intended for Jingju vocal source separation research, it includes separated tracks of vocals and main instruments from the Jingju arias. Consequently, the actual total duration of the ground truth recordings reached 24 hours and 56 minutes. These numerous separated recordings provide the JMTRC with the potential for in-depth research on Jingju vocal source separation. Table 2 shows the duration distribution of audio files within the JMTRC.

3.2.1 Coverage, completeness, quality and reusability

As previously mentioned, the purpose of JMTRC is for Jingju vocal source separation research. Based on this, the JMTRC was assessed according to four key criteria—coverage, completeness, quality, and reusability—following the definitions provided by Xavier et al. for the CompMusic Project in [40].

Coverage: The JMTRC has been developed to address the challenges of vocal source separation in Jingju music, providing individual tracks for the essential instruments, *jinghu*

¹刘希遮, responsible for the recording from Room 1, recording engineer of Linyi Workers’ Cultural Center. (7 years experience in audio engineering)

万荣斌, responsible for the recording from Room 2, Professional recording Engineer at Shandong Television Station. (20 years of experience in audio engineering)

Table 2: Duration Distribution of Audio Files

Track-type	Number of .wav	Total duration	Date-type	Note
vocals	45	4 h 5 min 44s	ground truth	
<i>jinghu</i>	45	4 h 5 min 44 s	ground truth	
<i>jingerhu</i>	39	3 h 34 min 20 s	ground truth	
<i>yueqin</i>	41	3 h 44 min 29 s	ground truth	
<i>zhongruan</i>	42	3 h 47 min 25 s	ground truth	
<i>daruan</i>	1	4 min 21 s	ground truth	
<i>sanxian</i>	2	9 min 47 s	ground truth	
percussion	45	4 h 5 min 50s	ground truth	
others	3	18 min 16 s	ground truth	In some arias, <i>zhongruan</i> , <i>daruan</i> , <i>yueqin</i> , and <i>sanxian</i> did not make split-track recordings.
accompaniment	45	4 h 5 min 44 s	mixig	
mixture	45	4 h 5 min 44 s	mixig	

and *yueqin*. It should be noted that the invited recording bands do not customarily use the *sanxian* when accompanying Jingju, resulting in relatively few *sanxian* recordings in the JMTRC. To enhance the JMTRC’s diversity and practical application, independent tracks of the *jingerhu* and *zhongruan* are also included, despite these instruments not being traditionally categorized among the three main instruments. While the primary focus is on the melodic arrangement, elements of the percussion arrangement have also been recorded, albeit in smaller quantities. All primary instruments and vocals feature over four hours of recorded material individually, ensuring that the data provides a solid foundation for fine-tuning source separation models and supports the validation and refinement of sophisticated source separation algorithms. Additionally, the JMTRC includes a diverse representation of the Jingju performance characteristics with a total of 5 different role- types, 6 unique *shengqiang*, and 14 distinct *banshi*, detailed collectively in Appendix A, Table 10.

Completeness: The JMTRC comprises audio files in .wav format, meticulously accompanied by expert annotations provided by specialists in Jingju. The author of this thesis has significantly enhanced the structure of the JMTRC by standardizing what was initially a disorganized collection. Each audio file is systematically organized and named according to a specific format, such as `BaWangBieJi_QuanJunWang_vocals_20240501_v1.wav`, which includes the Jingju play name, name of aria, type of recording (e.g., vocals), date, and version number. The files are then stored in folders named according to the play and arias, for example, `BaWangBieJi_QuanJunWang`. This reorganization greatly enhances the JMTRC's structural integrity and accessibility, thereby providing substantial benefits for future researchers. Moreover, the metadata accompanying each aria, provided in .txt format, includes the complete Chinese lyrics, annotated with detailed information about the *shengqiang*, *banshi*, and character and player roles.

Quality: Although the recording was conducted in two different environments, both rooms are professional recording studios equipped with recording equipment that meets professional standards, as shown in set 1 and set 2 in Section 3.1.2. Throughout the multitrack recording process of the JMTRC, extensive measures were taken to minimize interference between tracks, effectively preventing any track leakage. These measures significantly enhanced the quality of the recordings. Additionally, to ensure the recording quality of the JMTRC, two experts in Chinese Jingju, both State First-Class Artists, were invited to supervise the entire recording process and provide a detailed evaluation of the final recorded data. Their assessments confirmed that the data quality of the JMTRC met our expected standards.

Reusability: The JMTRC is now accessible on Zenodo ², providing the academic community and researchers with an invaluable resource for studying, analyzing, and learning about Jingju music. All audio and metadata files in the JMTRC are licensed under the Creative Commons Attribution Non Commercial No Derivatives 4.0 International (CC BY-NC-ND 4.0) license. It is important to note that the JMTRC is exclusively for non-commercial use and is not permitted for any commercial applications. Users are required to rigorously follow the specified usage regulations, ensuring the dataset is utilized solely for educational and research purposes.

²<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13580365>

3.2.2 Potential of the dataset

This dataset is not merely suitable for Jingju vocal source separation tasks; it also serves as an invaluable asset for research in Music Information Retrieval (MIR) and computational ethnomusicology, thanks to its extensive multitrack recording data. These high-quality recordings, paired with advanced MIR techniques such as pitch and melody extraction, facilitate intricate research into the playing techniques of the Jinghu, the dynamic interaction between the *jinghu* and vocal performances, and the identification of distinct Jingju roles, instruments, and individual artistic styles.

Furthermore, this dataset can significantly enhance deep learning and other machine learning models by addressing the critical shortage of high-quality traditional Chinese music data in existing models, like music generation, music recommendation. In the realm of arts and cultural preservation, these recordings help preserve Jingju's cultural heritage from the erosion of time. They provide global access for researchers and enthusiasts to explore this unique musical genre, ensuring its endurance and study across the world.

Thus, the dataset holds substantial potential and value, forging new pathways for a wide spectrum of academic inquiry and cultural preservation endeavors.

Chapter 4

Music Source Separation Implementation on Jingju

4.1 Methodology

4.1.1 Applying MUSDB18-Trained Models for Jingju Music Source Separation

In this phase, to validate the effectiveness of source separation models trained on pop music when applied to Jingju music and to establish a performance benchmark, the CWS-PresUnet and fine-tuned Sparse HT Demucs models were selected due to their strong performance on the MUSDB18 dataset. The average SDR of these models on this dataset is 6.77 dB and 9.20 dB, respectively, with vocal separation SDRs of 8.92 dB and 9.37 dB¹. Given that these models require significant computational resources (for instance, CWS-PresUnet requires eight V100 GPUs for 60 hours), pre-trained versions of these models² were used to assess their performance on the Jingju music dataset described in Chapter 3.

Given that the Band-split RNN model, despite achieving higher SI-SDR scores in published studies, was ultimately excluded from this research due to its high training costs

¹<https://paperswithcode.com/sota/music-source-separation-on-musdb18>

²<https://github.com/facebookresearch/demucs>

<https://github.com/haoheliu/2021-ismir-mss-challenge-cws-presunet>

and the unavailability of the additional music data required for training. The Spleeter [15] model was also included in the comparison because it has shown promising results after being fine-tuned on Indian Carnatic music, and its performance on Jingju music was evaluated as well.

The overall SI-SDR for the entire dataset was compared to evaluate the models' performance. Additionally, to compare the performance of the three models in terms of separation details, the fraction of SI-SDR values less than 1.5 dB, expressed as a percentage of the total, was analyzed.

4.1.2 Analyzing Performance Limitations

In this phase of the research, the impact of different instruments on vocal separation was analyzed. Using the *librosa* [41] library in Python, specific instrument tracks were removed from Jingju music by subtracting the corresponding track from the *mixture.wav* file, generating multiple audio variants, each lacking one instrument track. Vocal source separation was then re-applied using three models trained on pop music: Spleeter, CWS-PresUnet, and Sparse HT Demucs. After separation, the vocal separation SI-SDR for each processed audio file was recalculated to assess the quality of separation.

To further investigate the audio features affecting vocal separation quality, the fundamental frequency (F_0), spectral centroid, and Mel-Frequency Cepstral Coefficients (MFCC) were extracted from both the vocal and instrument tracks. The fundamental frequency was measured using *Torchcrepe*³, a deep learning-based pitch extraction library built on PyTorch, while the spectral centroid and MFCC were extracted using *librosa*'s built-in tools. The fundamental frequency distributions for each aria were also analyzed. Additionally, statistical tests were performed to examine the relationship between these features and the SI-SDR. Pearson correlation coefficients were calculated for each feature, and t-tests were conducted to verify the statistical significance of the results. All analyses were conducted using Python.

³<https://github.com/maxrmorrison/torchcrepe>

4.1.3 Fine-tuned Models with Jingju Dataset

In this phase of the research, we primarily investigate whether fine-tuning existing source separation models trained on pop music can enhance their performance in separating detailed components (i.e., reducing the proportion of SI-SDR values below 1.5 dB). To this end, we selected the CWS-PresUnet model for fine-tuning experiments because, as mentioned in Chapter 5, the CWS-PresUnet model trained on the MUSDB18 HB dataset exhibited the best performance when directly applied to the Jingju dataset. Additionally, the computational cost of fine-tuning the CWS-PresUnet model is manageable, requiring two days of training with eight V100 GPUs.

The fine-tuning data is derived from the Jingju source separation dataset constructed in Chapter 3, divided into a training set and a test set in an 8:2 ratio. The training set is used to fine-tune the CWS-PresUnet model, and the fine-tuned model is evaluated using both objective and subjective metrics. Objective evaluation metrics include SI-SDR and the proportion of vocal SI-SDR values below 1.5 dB, while subjective evaluation involves expert ratings on the quality of the audio separation.

To further investigate the impact of data volume on the effectiveness of model fine-tuning, we progressively reduce the amount of data used for fine-tuning by 25%, 50%, and 75% to determine whether optimal Jingju source separation performance can be achieved with minimal data. This research not only aims to enhance the performance of existing models but also provides important insights for future low-cost training of source separation models applicable to other music genres.

4.2 Experimental Setup

This section outlines the specific hardware and software environment used for the experiments, along with details of the experimental parameters.

The experiments were conducted on a system equipped with 8 AV100 GPUs, 14 virtual CPUs from an Intel(R) Xeon(R) Gold 6348 CPU @ 2.60GHz, and 100 GB of RAM. The software environment comprised Python 3.8 and the PyTorch 2.3 framework.

This experiment employed the CWS-PresUnet model for fine-tuning, utilizing a down-

sampled sub-band signal at 11.05 kHz. The Short-Time Fourier Transform (STFT) was computed with a window length of 512 samples and a hop size of 110 samples. The model was trained over a total of 50 epochs using the Adam optimizer with an initial learning rate of 0.001, applying exponential decay throughout the training process.

The dataset used for training and evaluation, as detailed in Chapter 3, provided mixture recordings and isolated vocal and instrumental tracks which constitute the mixture.

All training scripts and the pre-trained models will be made available on GitHub ⁴.

4.3 Evaluation

4.3.1 Objective Evaluation

Objective evaluation of source separation typically uses three metrics proposed by Emmanuel et al. in [42]: Source to Distortion Ratio (SDR), Source to Interference Ratio (SIR), and Source to Artifact Ratio (SAR). These metrics provide a comprehensive assessment of the models' performance in separating sources from mixed audio signals.

Under general circumstances, the estimated source signal \hat{s} from the mixed signal can be decomposed into four components:

$$\hat{s} = s_{\text{target}} + e_{\text{interf}} + e_{\text{noise}} + e_{\text{artif}} \quad (4.1)$$

where s_{target} is the estimate of the target source signal, s_{interf} is the interference caused by other source signals, e_{noise} is the noise, and e_{artif} is the artifact introduced by the algorithm.

The Source to Distortion Ratio (SDR) is a metric used to assess the similarity between the separated target source signal and the original target source signal. It is a common measure for evaluating the performance of source separation algorithms. The formula for SDR is given by:

$$\text{SDR} = 10 \log_{10} \frac{\|s_{\text{target}}\|^2}{\|e_{\text{interf}} + e_{\text{noise}} + e_{\text{artif}}\|^2} \quad (4.2)$$

⁴www.github

The Source to Interference Ratio (SIR) evaluates the impact of interference from other sources on the target signal. It is calculated using the following formula:

$$\text{SIR} = 10 \log_{10} \frac{\|s_{\text{target}}\|^2}{\|e_{\text{interf}}\|^2} \quad (4.3)$$

The Source to Artifact Ratio (SAR) measures the extent to which artifacts introduced by the separation algorithm affect the source signal. It is defined as:

$$\text{SAR} = 10 \log_{10} \frac{\|s_{\text{target}} + e_{\text{interf}} + e_{\text{noise}}\|^2}{\|e_{\text{artif}}\|^2} \quad (4.4)$$

However, in modern source separation tasks, especially those employing deep neural networks, models often adjust the amplitude of output signals. In source separation, the absolute amplitude of signals is less critical than the fidelity of the signal's structure and content. The traditional Signal to Distortion Ratio (SDR) is highly susceptible to amplitude variations, which can skew performance evaluation.

To address this issue, the Scale-Invariant Signal to Distortion Ratio (SI-SDR) was introduced by Le Roux et al. [43]. SI-SDR has become a mainstream metric for evaluating source separation performance as it disregards amplitude changes, focusing instead on the quality and distortion of the signal. This approach provides a more accurate and appropriate evaluation standard for source separation tasks, highlighting the true performance of the separation model without being affected by amplitude scaling. It is given by:

$$\text{SI-SDR} = 10 \log_{10} \frac{\|\alpha \cdot s_{\text{target}}\|^2}{\|\alpha \cdot s_{\text{target}} - s\|^2} \quad (4.5)$$

where α is the scaling factor obtained by minimizing the power error, defined as $\alpha = \frac{\langle s, s_{\text{target}} \rangle}{\|s_{\text{target}}\|^2}$.

In this thesis, SI-SDR is employed as the primary evaluation metric to ensure that the performance of the source separation models is accurately assessed. The SI-SDR values are calculated using the Python library `speechmetrics`⁵, providing a robust and consistent

⁵<https://github.com/SonginMoonlight/Jingju-Vocal-Source-Separation>

standard for comparison.

4.3.2 Subjective Evaluation

In the subjective evaluation conducted in this study, the Mushra-like Online Comparison (MOC) method was employed, utilizing a specially designed online platform to assess seven different audio segments of Beijing opera systematically. Each segment included three differently processed vocal versions: one from a model without fine-tuning, another from the same model post-fine-tuning, and a third serving as the ground truth audio for benchmarking. Four of these segments were derived from a commercial database, while the remaining three originated from a dataset constructed for this research, specifically designed to test the model's performance in real-world scenarios. To ensure a rigorous assessment of the audio samples, participants were selectively recruited based on their musical backgrounds, particularly those with expertise or a strong interest in Beijing opera. This targeted selection was aimed at leveraging the participants' intrinsic understanding of the genre's unique characteristics, thereby enhancing the reliability and relevance of the feedback received. The evaluation criteria included clarity of audio quality, background music leakage, and artifacts introduced by the separation process, which together provided a comprehensive measure of the model's performance.

In a standardized listening environment, participants listened to different versions of each segment through headphones and rated each version on a scale from 1 to 5, where 1 represented the lowest and 5 the highest score. This rating reflected the overall quality and effectiveness of the source separation. The online interface of the survey procedure is depicted in Figure 13 of Appendix A.

The collected ratings were statistically analyzed, calculating average scores and standard deviations for each audio version. Statistical T-test was utilized to evaluate significant differences in model performance before and after fine-tuning, with a particular focus on the nuanced perceptions of participants familiar with musical and operatic forms.

Chapter 5

Result and Discussion

This chapter presents the results of applying pop music source separation models to Jingju music, analyzing performance limitations, and examining the impact of pitch and timbre on vocal separation. It provides a comprehensive discussion of the findings and their implications.

1) *Applying Pop Music Source Separation Models on Jingju*: As detailed in Section 4.1.1, this phase initially computed the Scale-Invariant Signal to Distortion Ratio (SI-SDR) for vocal and accompaniment separation using three pre-trained models on the MUSDB18 dataset. These models were subsequently applied to the Jingju dataset, and the SI-SDR for both vocal and accompaniment separation was recalculated. The differences between the SI-SDR values from the MUSDB18 and Jingju datasets were computed, with comparison results presented in Table 3.

Model	Pop Music		Jingju		Difference	
	vocals	acc	vocals	acc	vocals	acc
Spleeter	5.2412	12.2955	5.497	4.5051	-0.2558	7.7904
CWS-PResUnet	6.9182	14.2006	8.1392	7.2438	-1.221	6.9568
Sparse Ht-Demucs	8.1926	13.6246	8.1392	7.2438	0.0534	6.3808

Table 3: SI-SDR (dB) results for different source separation models on Pop Music and Jingju datasets, including the differences.

The Spleeter and CWS-PResUnet models, both trained on pop music, generally achieve improved vocal source separation on the Jingju dataset compared to their

performance on pop music. In contrast, the Sparse HT-Demucs model, which shows the best performance in vocal separation for pop music, exhibits a decline in effectiveness when applied to Jingju music, suggesting potential overfitting to pop music characteristics. All three models demonstrated a significant decline in performance when separating accompaniment in the Jingju dataset.

To analyze separation performance in more detail, Table 4 presents the percentage of SI-SDR values below 1.5 dB for the three models in the Jingju source separation task. The findings reveal a significant proportion of SI-SDR values below 1.5 dB in the vocal separation task, underscoring the models’ limitations in handling intricate sound details during separation.

Model	Percentage with SI-SDR Below 1.5 dB	
	vocals	accompaniment
Spleeter	31.49%	9.67%
CWS-PResUnet	28.54%	1.12%
Sparse Ht-Demucs	29.21%	1.74%

Table 4: Percentage of samples with SI-SDR below 1.5 dB for different models.

In summary, source separation models trained on pop music generally perform well in the vocal separation task for Jingju. However, the unique challenges of Jingju music arise from high timbral similarity and dynamic interaction between vocals and accompaniment. These challenges are exacerbated by the need to manage subtle pitch variations, dynamic range, and the complex blending of timbres, such as the similarities between the *jinghu* and human vocals. As a result, a significant proportion of the vocal separation SI-SDR values fall below 1.5 dB, indicating difficulties in accurately separating these components.

To make this more intuitive, several Jingju arias (e.g., “Xie Yao Huan”, “Xi Feng Lie”, “Zha Mei An”) were separated using the CWS-PResUnet model. The segments where the SI-SDR for vocal separation is less than 1.5 dB were labeled in the original ground truth track. Figure 9 shows the visualization for “Xie Yao Huan”. Additional visualizations are provided in Figure 14 in Appendix B. It can be seen that most places where the SI-SDR is less than 1.5 dB have no vocals, indicating that the model incorrectly separates a vocal-like instrument into the vocal track.

Figure 9: Visualization segments with SI-SDR below 1.5 dB in Xie Yao Huan.

- 2) *Analyzing Performance Limitations*: Firstly, as detailed in Section 4.1.2, the impact of different instruments on vocal separation was analyzed by subtracting the corresponding tracks from the overall mixture file. Subsequently, vocal source separation was performed, and the corresponding changes in SI-SDR were calculated. The resulting data was subjected to t-tests and Pearson correlation coefficient calculations. The results are shown in Table 5.

Statistical results indicate that the removal of the *jinghu* significantly improves the SI-SDR of vocal separation across all models. For the Spleeter model, removing the *jinghu* increased the mean SI-SDR to 2.033 dB with a standard deviation of 2.015, a t-value of 6.77 ($p < 0.05$), and a Pearson correlation coefficient of 0.85 ($p < 0.05$), indicating a strong positive correlation between *jinghu* removal and SI-SDR improvement. For the CWS-PResUnet model, the mean SI-SDR after removing the *jinghu* was 2.671 dB, with a t-value of 7.463 ($p < 0.05$) and a Pearson correlation coefficient of 0.316 ($p < 0.05$), also showing a positive correlation. Similarly, the Sparse HT-Demucs model showed significant improvement, with a mean SI-SDR of 1.243 dB, a t-value of 3.519 ($p < 0.05$), and a Pearson correlation coefficient of 0.656 ($p < 0.05$).

Additionally, the removal of other instruments such as the *jingerhu*, *yueqin*, *zhongruan*, and percussion instruments also impacted SI-SDR. For the Spleeter model, removing the *jingerhu*, in addition to the *jinghu*, showed a significant positive cor-

relation with SI-SDR improvement, with a Pearson correlation coefficient of 0.742 ($p < 0.05$). Conversely, removing the *zhongruan* resulted in a significant decrease in SI-SDR, with a Pearson correlation coefficient of -0.732 ($p < 0.05$), indicating a strong negative correlation. In the Sparse HT-Demucs model, the removal of the *zhongruan* and percussion instruments also had significant impacts, with Pearson correlation coefficients of -0.804 and -0.781, respectively, both showing significant negative correlations ($p < 0.05$).

These results reveal the significant impact of the *jinghu* on vocal separation SI-SDR, demonstrating that the acoustic similarity between the *jinghu* and vocals in Jingju leads to its incorrect separation as vocals. As described in Section 1.3.2, the essence of the *jinghu* lies in mimicking the stylistic features of the singer, resulting in sounds that are very similar to vocals in terms of pitch range, timbre, and cadential structure.

Model	Removed Instrument	Mean	STD	T-val	P-val	Corr.	P-val
Spleeter	<i>jinghu</i>	2.03	2.01	6.77	2.49e-8**	0.85	1.90e-4*
	<i>jingerhu</i>	0.27	1.48	-3.49	1.12e-3	0.74	5.60e-9
	<i>yueqin</i>	0.18	1.76	0.66	0.511	0.58	7.48e-5
	<i>zhongruan</i>	-1.13	1.28	-5.70	1.17e-6	0.73	3.55e-8
	percussion	-0.66	1.26	-3.49	2.49e-8	1.1e-3	5.60e-9
CWS- PResUnet	<i>jinghu</i>	2.67	2.40	7.46	2.41e-9***	0.32	3.43e-2*
	<i>jingerhu</i>	1.37	2.07	4.13	1.92e-4	0.34	3.54e-2
	<i>yueqin</i>	0.23	2.00	0.73	0.470	0.42	6.68e-3
	<i>zhongruan</i>	-0.58	1.64	-2.29	2.71e-2	0.57	9.46e-5
	percussion	-0.58	1.64	-2.29	2.71e-2	0.57	9.46e-5
Sparse Ht Demucs	<i>jinghu</i>	1.24	2.37	3.52	1.02e-3*	0.66	1.01e-3*
	<i>jingerhu</i>	-0.46	1.90	-1.52	0.137	0.76	1.50e-8
	<i>yueqin</i>	-0.37	2.10	-1.11	0.272	0.69	5.26e-7
	<i>zhongruan</i>	-1.72	1.86	-5.97	4.77e-7	0.80	1.48e-10
	percussion	-1.36	1.84	-4.93	1.20e-5	0.78	1.20e-5

Table 5: Statistical summary of SI-SDR differences after removal of different instruments. Significant P-values are marked with asterisks: * indicates $p < 0.05$, ** indicates $p < 0.01$, and *** indicates $p < 0.001$.

Based on the above analysis results, the study next focuses on a detailed analysis of pitch and timbre in Jingju arias. The fundamental frequencies (F_0) of full and falsetto voices, as well as the *jinghu*, were calculated and analyzed for their F_0 distributions and overlap rates between the two types of voices. Statistical analysis revealed a

significant correlation between vocal separation performance (measured by SI-SDR) and the F_0 overlap rate (see Table 6).

	Falsetto (N=26)	Full Voice (N=19)	Overall
Overlap			
Mean	33.39	16.45	26.24
Std Dev	7.59	12.06	9.48
t-test p-value		5.39, p=9.30e-06	
Si-SDR (Spleeter)			
Mean	4.89	6.31	5.49
Std Dev	1.95	1.25	1.66
t-test p-value		-2.97, p=4.94e-3	
Pearson Correlation p-value		-0.41, p=4.86e-3	
Si-SDR (CWS-PResUnet)			
Mean	7.61	8.85	8.13
Std Dev	2.25	1.55	1.95
t-test p-value		-2.19, p=3.40e-2	
Pearson Correlation		-0.48, p=8.528e-4	
Si-SDR (Sparse HT Demucs)			
Mean	6.65	9.50	7.85
Std Dev	2.80	1.49	2.25
t-test p-value		-4.41, p=7.53e-5	
Pearson Correlation		-0.62, p=6.95e-6	

Table 6: Descriptive statistics and correlation analysis of SI-SDR and fundamental frequency overlap in Jingju vocal source separation between Jinghu and vocal parts in different vocal modes.

The data show that the Mean F_0 overlap rate between falsetto voices and the *jinghu* is 33.39, significantly higher than the 16.45 for full voices (independent sample t-test, t-value = 5.39, $p < 0.05$). In terms of vocal separation performance, the Mean SI-SDR for falsetto voices (4.89 dB, 7.61 dB, and 6.65 dB) is significantly lower than that for full voices (6.31 dB, 8.85 dB, and 9.50 dB) (independent sample t-test t-values = -2.97, -2.19, and -4.41, all $p < 0.05$). Additionally, by calculating the Pearson correlation coefficients between the SI-SDR of vocal separation and the F_0 overlap rate for the three models, the results are -0.41, -0.47, and -0.61 (all $p < 0.05$), indicating that increased F_0 overlap is often associated with a decrease in SI-SDR, a relationship more pronounced in falsetto voices.

These findings indicate that the similarity in F_0 between falsetto voices in Jingju and the *jinghu* is higher, leading to poorer separation performance by source separation

models trained on pop music when processing falsetto Jingju arias. Therefore, the performance of vocal source separation is poorer for falsetto voices compared to full voices in Jingju roles.

To visually present these analysis results, Figure 10 shows the temporal changes and distributions of F_0 for vocals and the *jinghu* in arias of the two voice types. The figure clearly shows that the F_0 distribution of vocals tends to be lower than that of the *jinghu* when using full voices, which aligns with the singing characteristics of *laosheng*, *laodan*, and *jing* roles in Jingju—voices that are rich and deep. Figure 15 and Figure 16 in Appendix B provide additional arias and their related F0 distributions and separation effects to reinforce the conclusions of this study.

In the analysis of timbre and its impact on vocal separation performance, no significant statistical correlation was found between Mel-Frequency Cepstral Coefficients (MFCC) or spectral centroid and vocal separation SI-SDR. This lack of correlation may be due to the inherent subtlety and variability of timbre characteristics, which makes these features difficult to quantify accurately. Despite this, human listeners can perceive a notable difference in timbre between falsetto and full voice singing.

Aria	Original (dB)	After Fine-tuning (dB)	Difference (dB)	Original Below 1.5dB (%)	After Fine-tuning Below 1.5dB (%)	Difference (%)
Xi Feng Lie	2.91	14.15	11.25	34.48	22.17	12.31
Xi Xiang Ji - Zhen Mei Jiu	4.98	13.82	8.84	22.73	22.19	0.54
Xie Yao Huan	5.57	16.04	10.47	13.72	2.74	10.98
Yang Men Nv Jiang	4.20	14.29	10.10	24.02	5.92	18.10
Yu Zhou Feng	6.59	15.81	9.22	40.19	24.69	15.50
Zha Mei An	6.76	14.73	7.97	42.67	5.37	37.30
Zhi Qu Wei Hu Shan	4.60	11.78	7.18	14.65	7.21	7.44
Zhuo Fang Cao	6.49	15.75	9.26	27.74	0.73	27.01
Overall	5.26	14.55	9.28	26.27	9.91	26.17

Table 7: Comparison of SI-SDR before and after fine-tuning the CWS-PreUnet model and the percentage below 1.5dB.

3) *Fine-tuned Models with Jingju Dataset*: The test results of the fine-tuned CWS-PreUnet model on selected Jingju arias are shown in Table 7. It can be seen that the performance of the fine-tuned CWS-PreUnet model in vocal source separation for Jingju has significantly improved, with a noticeable increase in SI-SDR and a marked decrease in the proportion of vocal SI-SDR values below 1.5 dB.

To visualize this result, the SI-SDR values below 1.5 dB for the separated vocals of

(a) Pitch tracking and pitch distribution in Zhuo Fang Cao (Vocal type: full voice).

(b) Pitch tracking and pitch distribution in Hai Gang (Vocal type: falsetto).

Figure 10: Comparison of vocal and *jinghu* pitch in different vocal type Jingju arias.

the same Jingju aria before and after fine-tuning are plotted, as shown in Figure 11. It is evident that the portions of separated vocals with SI-SDR below 1.5 dB have significantly decreased in the same segment after fine-tuning.

(a) The CWS-PresUnet separates out the portion of the vocal SI-SDR below 1.5 dB (before fine-tuning).

(b) The CWS-PresUnet separates out the portion of the vocal SI-SDR below 1.5 dB (after fine-tuning).

Figure 11: Comparison of performance on Xie Yao Huan before and after fine-tuning the CWS-PresUnet model.

Building on the quantitative analysis, a subjective evaluation was also conducted to more comprehensively assess the model's performance and the perceptual quality of the separated vocals. A total of 27 valid subjective evaluations were collected for this study. To ensure the validity and reliability of the data, the questionnaires were screened by detecting anomalies in ground truth scores and evaluating the total time taken to complete them. Specifically, questionnaires were deemed invalid if they showed abnormally low scores across multiple ground truth items and had completion times outside a reasonable range. Figure 12 presents the demographic distribution of participants after this screening process. Based on the validated subjective scoring

data, a statistical analysis was conducted, and the results are presented in Table 8.

Figure 12: Distribution of music backgrounds among participants in the subjective evaluation.

Table 8: Evaluation metrics of different Arias before and after fine-tuning. Note: CD denotes the Commercial Dataset. Significant P-values are marked with asterisks: * indicates $p < 0.05$, ** indicates $p < 0.01$, and *** indicates $p < 0.001$

Aria	Fine Tuning	Audio Quality			BGM Leakage			Artifacts			Source
		Mean	T-val	P-val	Mean	T-val	P-val	Mean	T-val	P-val	
Shang Tian Tai	after	4.85	5.2**	0**	4	2.71*	0.012*	4.35	3.45*	0.002**	JMTRC
	before	4.15			3.27			3.62			
Zhuo Fang Cao	after	4.85	3.07*	0.005**	4.31	3.17*	0.004**	4.19	2.29*	0.031*	JMTRC
	before	4.42			3.42			3.73			
Zhi Qu Wei Hu Shan	after	4.27	2.6*	0.015*	3.92	1.25	0.223	4.04	0.39	0.703	CD
	before	3.81			3.58			3.96			
Yang Men Nv Jiang	after	4.58	2.48*	0.02*	4.15	3.45*	0.002**	4.27	4.07*	0**	CD
	before	4.08			3.27			3.38			
Sha Jia Bang	after	4.38	0.65	0.523	3.58	-0.25	0.805	3.81	0.47	0.64	JMTRC
	before	4.27			3.35			3.69			
Zhuang Yuan Mei	after	4.58	1.92	0.067	4.04	3.39*	0.002**	4.15	1.76	0.091	JMTRC
	before	4.19			2.88			3.65			
Zha Mei An	after	4.50	1	0.327	4.27	4.81*	0**	4.19	2.22*	0.036*	CD
	before	4.31			3.04			3.58			

Based on Table 8, the subjective evaluation of the quality of extracted vocals from various Jingju arias before and after fine-tuning reveals significant differences in model performance. For **Audio Quality**, fine-tuning resulted in notable improvements for “Shang Tian Tai”, “Zhuo Fang Cao”, and “Yang Men Nv Jiang”, with mean scores increasing to 4.85, 4.85, and 4.58, respectively, and corresponding p-values below 0.05. These results indicate that fine-tuning effectively enhances vocal clarity for these specific arias. In contrast, arias such as “Sha Jia Bang” and “Zha Mei An” exhibit non-significant changes ($p > 0.05$), suggesting a limited impact of fine-tuning

on these pieces. The commercial dataset aria “Zhi Qu Wei Hu Shan” shows a p -value of 0.015 for Audio Quality, suggesting moderate improvement, whereas Zha Mei An shows no significant change ($p = 0.327$), highlighting variability in fine-tuning effectiveness depending on dataset characteristics.

Regarding Background Music (BGM) Leakage, fine-tuning significantly reduces leakage in “Shang Tian Tai”, “Zhuo Fang Cao”, and “Yang Men Nv Jiang”, as indicated by p -values below 0.05, with mean scores rising to 4.00, 4.31, and 4.15, respectively. These findings suggest that the fine-tuned model effectively suppresses background interference in these arias. “Zha Mei An” also demonstrates a significant reduction in BGM leakage after fine-tuning ($p < 0.01$), further confirming the process’s effectiveness. However, “Zhi Qu Wei Hu Shan” and “Sha Jia Bang” do not show significant improvements in BGM leakage ($p > 0.05$), suggesting that further optimization may be required for these arias to achieve better results.

For **Artifacts**, fine-tuning significantly prevents the introduction of unwanted artifacts in “Shang Tian Tai”, “Zhuo Fang Cao”, and “Yang Men Nv Jiang”, with p -values indicating strong significance ($p < 0.05$). This suggests that fine-tuning effectively enhances the vocal separation process by avoiding distortions or unnatural sounds. “Zha Mei An” also shows a significant decrease in artifacts ($p < 0.05$), further supporting the benefits of fine-tuning. Conversely, “Sha Jia Bang” and “Zhi Qu Wei Hu Shan” show no significant change in artifacts ($p > 0.05$), indicating that these arias may require more targeted fine-tuning strategies to achieve similar levels of performance. Overall, the results suggest that fine-tuning markedly enhances the model’s performance in separating vocals from Jingju mixture recordings, particularly in terms of audio quality and background music suppression, especially for the JMTRC dataset. In contrast, while the fine-tuning does not perform as well on the commercial dataset as it does on the JMTRC dataset, it still achieves relatively good vocal separation performance given the differences in recording quality, noise levels, and the complexity of the musical arrangements.

Chapter 6

Conclusion

The core of this study is the development and optimization of source separation models specifically for Jingju music. To achieve this, a new dedicated multitrack dataset (JMTRC) for Jingju music was constructed, comprising professionally mixed full Jingju recordings and their corresponding individual tracks, such as isolated vocal recordings, *jinghu* recordings, and *jingerhu* recordings. This dataset serves as the foundation for training and evaluating various Jingju source separation models, including those initially designed for pop music. Moreover, the dataset lays a foundation for future computational ethnomusicology research related to Jingju.

Subsequently, using this dataset, the study fine-tuned an existing model, CWS-PresUnet, which was originally developed for source separation in pop music. The results demonstrate that fine-tuning the model on a domain-specific dataset significantly enhances its ability to separate vocals from Jingju music, as reflected in both objective metrics, such as SI-SDR, and subjective perceptual quality measures. One of the key reasons why source separation models trained on pop music, like those using MUSDB18, do not perform well on Jingju music is due to the unique musicological characteristics of Jingju. Instruments like the *jinghu* in Jingju music share a high degree of similarity with vocals in terms of pitch range, leading these models to mistakenly identify Jinghu sounds as vocals during separation, resulting in errors.

6.1 Limitations

- 1) **Limited Recording Quality and Coverage of the Dataset:** Although the dataset built in this study includes various Jingju arias and their corresponding accompaniment recordings, its coverage remains limited, and the overall duration is insufficient to fully represent the complete range and variations of Jingju styles. Additionally, due to recording constraints, certain percussion instruments (e.g., gong, *bangu*) were not recorded on separate tracks. The presence of excessive reverberation in some recordings also negatively affects the dataset quality and, consequently, the model's performance.
- 2) **Impact of Dataset Limitations on Model Fine-Tuning:** The constraints of the dataset may have affected the fine-tuning performance of the models, potentially preventing them from achieving optimal results. This limitation is particularly evident when the models are tested with Jingju recordings from some commercial datasets, where performance tends to decline. This indicates that there is still room for improvement in the diversity and quality of audio samples in the current dataset to better support model fine-tuning and performance optimization.
- 3) **Lack of Use of the Best-Performing Source Separation Models:** The source separation model selected for fine-tuning is not the best-performing model available for pop music separation tasks. For example, while the Band-split RNN model performs best in pop music separation tasks, it was not included in this study due to the unavailability of a pre-trained Band-split RNN model for vocal separation. This limitation might have constrained the upper bound of the research results and prevented the study from fully demonstrating potential improvements using more advanced models.
- 4) **Insufficient Comprehensive Musicological Analysis:** When analyzing why source separation models trained on pop music perform poorly on Jingju, this study primarily focused on pitch range. However, the similarity between Jingju vocals and Jinghu extends beyond pitch to include rhythm and timbre, which may also significantly impact separation performance. Due to the lack of direct statistical evidence linking other musicological features with separation outcomes, the depth and comprehen-

siveness of the analysis in this study are limited.

- 5) **Limited Number of Subjects in Subjective Analysis Tests:** The number of subjects in the subjective evaluation tests was relatively small, with only 27 participants. The Jingju excerpts used in these tests were also limited, which may affect the representativeness and reliability of the test results and conclusions. Future research should consider increasing the sample size and diversity in subjective tests to more comprehensively assess model performance in vocal separation tasks.

6.2 Future Work

- 1) **Enhancing the Quality and Expanding the Scope of the JMTRC :** Future research should focus on further expanding the size and diversity of the JMTRC. By incorporating more Jingju recordings, especially by extending the separate recording tracks for accompanying instruments (e.g., single-track recordings of percussion instruments), the dataset can more comprehensively capture the various musical characteristics of Jingju. Improving the quality of these recordings by reducing unnecessary reverberation and background noise will also benefit model training and performance enhancement.
- 2) **Exploring the Dataset's Potential for Other Jingju-Related Research:** Beyond source separation tasks, the JMTRC can be leveraged for other Jingju-related research areas, such as Music Information Retrieval (MIR), automated music analysis, pitch and rhythm pattern recognition, among others. By extracting potential musicological information from the dataset, researchers can explore more features and structures of Jingju music, thereby promoting broader efforts in the digital preservation and transmission of Jingju culture.
- 3) **Fine-Tuning Superior Pop Music Source Separation Models:** Future work could explore fine-tuning current state-of-the-art source separation models that perform well on pop music, such as the Band-split RNN or other advanced deep learning architectures, using the Jingju multitrack dataset. Investigating whether fine-tuning these advanced models on a domain-specific dataset can significantly enhance Jingju

vocal separation performance could help identify more effective model optimization strategies.

- 4) **Deepening the Study of Pop Music Models' Adaptation Issues to Jingju:** Existing research has primarily focused on pitch features. Future studies could delve deeper into analyzing other reasons why source separation models trained on pop music do not perform well on Jingju, such as the timbral and rhythmic similarities between vocals and Jinghu. New experiments and analytical methods could be designed to explore how these musical features impact the separation performance, providing a more in-depth understanding.
- 5) **Increasing the Quantity and Diversity of Subjective Evaluations:** To more comprehensively assess the practical effectiveness of models in vocal separation tasks, future research should consider expanding the sample size and diversity of subjective evaluations. This could be achieved by incorporating more Jingju excerpts and recordings of different styles and recruiting more participants with a musical background. Such steps would improve the representativeness and reliability of subjective evaluations, ensuring the scientific rigor and broad applicability of the research conclusions.

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Appendix A

First Appendix

京剧人声源分离主观测试

京剧人声源分离是运用深度学习技术将完整京剧音频中的人声与背景音乐分开。本实验旨在对分离后的音频质量进行主观评估。整个实验时长在10分钟左右。请在安静的环境中进行此实验，并在条件允许的情况下使用耳机以确保评估的准确性。

在测试开始之前，您将先听到两段京剧音频，选自著名剧目《霸王别姬》。这些音频包括一段完整的京剧录音和相应的人声部分。您可以使用这两段音频来调整音量，确保音量适中，并对即将进行的测试有一个初步的理解。温馨提示：建议您从小到大逐渐调整音量，以避免对听力造成伤害。

《霸王别姬》完整录音

2.wav
- 00:00 / 00:13

《霸王别姬》纯人声

1.wav
- 00:00 / 00:13

***1 您的年龄**

12-18
 19-40
 40-65
 65岁以上

***2 您对京剧与音乐的了解程度**

专业京剧演员 (或接受过京剧专业训练)
 京剧爱好者 (票友)
 专业歌手与乐器演奏家 (或接受过相应训练)
 音频工程师
 音乐爱好者
 一般听众 (或对音乐不感兴趣)

您将听到六个京剧音频片段。每个片段包含2到3个不同的音频，每个音频持续10到40秒。请您根据听感，对以下几个方面进行评分：音频质量，背景音乐泄露 (无泄露得5分，泄露严重得1分)，以及是否有人为干预的痕迹 (无干预得5分，干预明显得1分)。请您从细节出发，为每个维度给出评分。

***3 上天台_1**

vocals.wav
- 00:00 / 00:58

	非常不满意 1	非常满意 5
音频质量	<input checked="" type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
背景音乐泄露	<input checked="" type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
人为痕迹	<input checked="" type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

***4 上天台_2**

vocals_1.wav
- 00:00 / 00:58

	非常不满意 1	非常满意 5
音频质量	<input checked="" type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
背景音乐泄露	<input checked="" type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
人为痕迹	<input checked="" type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

Figure 13: The online subjective test interface (partial)

Table 9: Recording configuration and aria allocation.

Recording equipment	Recording rooms	Arias' names
Set 1	Room 1	Ba Wang Bie Ji - Kan Da Wang, Ba Wang Bie Ji - Quan Jun Wang, Ba Zhen Tang, Bai She Zhuan, Chi Meng, Chun Gui Meng, Ci Wang Liao, Da Long Pao, Gui Fei Zui Jiu, Hai Gang, Hong Deng Ji, Hong Niang - Kan Xiao Jie, Hong Niang - Xiao Jie Ni, Hong Se Niang Zi Jun, Hong Yang Dong - Wei Guo Jia, Jiang Jie, Jin Yu Nu, Kong Cheng Ji, Liang Zhu, Long Jiang Song, Sha Jia Bang, Shang Tian Tai, Sheng Si Hen, Suo Lin Nang, Tian Xia Gui Xin, Wang Jiang Ting - Du Shou Kong, Xi Feng Lie, Xi Xiang Ji - Bi Yun Tian, Xi Xiang Ji - Zhen Mei Jiu, Xie Yao Huan, Yu Zhou Feng, Zhi Qu Wei Hu Shan, Zhuang Yuan Mei
Set 2	Room 2	Chi Sang Zhen, Diao Jin Gui, Feng Huan Chao, Hong Yang Dong - Tan Yang Jia, San Niang Jiao Zi, Sou Gu Jiu Gu, Tai Zhen Wai Zhuan, Wang Jiang Ting - Zhi Shuo Shi, Yang Men Nv Jiang, Yu Huang Hou, Zha Mei An, Zhuo Fang Cao

Table 10: Overview of Role-Types with *shengqiang* and *banshi* specifications.

Role-Type	Shengqiang	Banshi
dan (qingyi)	xipi, erhuang, nanbangzi, sipingdiao, fansipingdiao,	erliu, sanban, huidiao sanyan, manban, yaoban, yuanban, liushui, duoban, sanban, kuaisanyan, huilong, daoban fanerhuang
dan (huadan)	sipingdiao, fansipingdiao	
dan (laodan)	erhuang, xipi	daoban, manban, duoban, sanban, yuanban, liushui, sanyan, yaoban
sheng (laosheng)	erhuang, xipi, fanerhuang	sanyan, yuanban, manban, kuaiban, mansanyan
jing (hualian)	erhuang, xipi	daoban, yuanban, erliu, kuaiban, yaoban, sanban, pengban

Appendix B

Second Appendix

(a) The Xi Feng Lie.

(b) The Yu Zhou Feng.

(c) The Zha Nei An.

Figure 14: Visualization of SI-SDR below 1.5 dB for different arias.

(a) Pitch tracking and pitch distribution in Chi Sang Zhen.

(b) Pitch tracking and pitch distribution in Diao Jin Gui.

Figure 15: Comparison of vocal and *jinghu* pitch of full voice arias.

(a) Pitch tracking and pitch distribution in Yu Zhou Feng.

(b) Pitch tracking and pitch distribution in Jin Yu Nu.

Figure 16: Comparison of vocal and *jinghu* pitch of falsetto arias.